

A STUDY OF ANXIETY AND AGGRESSION OF BALL BADMINTON PLAYERS OF SPPU PUNE UNIVERSITY PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The main purpose of this study was to conduct the anxiety and aggression tests on Savitribai Phule Pune university ball badminton players. To achieve the purpose of the study data was collected from two hundred players, various four zones (Pune city, Pune district, Ahmednagar and Nasik) under jurisdiction of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune. The age of the subjects were ranging from 18-25 years are considered as the total sample (N=200) of the study. The data collected was treated with the statistical technique 't' and found there is a significant difference in the selected psychological aspects between four zones players under jurisdiction of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune.

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Key words: Psychology, Ball Badminton, anxiety and aggression.

Introduction:

The world of games and sports has crossed many milestones, as a result of different achievements in general and their application in the filled of sports in particular. Scientific investigation into performance of sportsman has been playing an increasingly importance role to attain excellence of performance in different sports. Sports psychology is all about sports behavior especially with muscle – minded interactions, that influences and their outcomes in the context of sport which is basically a form of active reaction. But which has turned intensely competitive on account of the growing Olympics well over a century.

Purpose of the Study:

The main purpose of the study was to the Psychological variables such as anxiety and aggression of Ball Badminton Players.

Methods and Materials:

The research tool for Competitive state Anxiety Inventory-2(CSAI-2) by Martens, Valley & Burton, (1990) Sport Aggression Inventory by Anand Kumar and Prem Shankar Shukla.

For the investigation the male and female Ball Badminton Players of various four zones (Pune city, Pune district, Ahmednagar and Nasik) under jurisdiction of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune aged between 18-25 years are considered as the total sample (N=200) of the study.

Statistical Method:-

The data collected was treated with the statistical technique 't' and results are presented in the following tables.

Result and Discussion:-

It was observed from the Sports Competitive State Anxiety and Aggression variable from table was shows that there was a mean difference between of the sample of 200 cases of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Zones of subjects regarding to the psychological variables.

Table No. 1

Descriptive Statistical of the Sports Competitive State Anxiety Variable for SPPU University, Zone wise Ball Badminton Boys & Girls Players

SPPU Zones	Nasik Zone Ball Badminton Players		Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton Players		Pune District Zone Ball Badminton Players		Pune City Zone Ball Badminton Players	
	Anxiety (CSAI-2)		Anxiety (CSAI-2)		Anxiety (CSAI-2)		Anxiety (CSAI-2)	
Variable	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
Number	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Mean	60.32	63.08	66.04	68.24	58.16	54.96	53.76	53.88
Std. Error of Mean	0.66	0.46	0.48	0.64	0.51	0.48	0.62	0.36
Median	60.00	63.00	66.00	68.00	58.00	56.00	54.00	54.00
Mode	60.00	62.00	65.00	68.00	58.00	56.00	54.00	54.00
Std. Deviation	3.31	2.34	2.44	3.21	2.57	2.42	3.12	1.83
Variance	10.97	5.49	5.95	10.35	6.64	5.87	9.77	3.36
Skewness	0.127	0.360	-0.237	0.025	0.237	-0.484	-0.221	-0.205
Std. Error of Skewness	0.464	0.446	0.464	0.464	0.446	0.464	0.464	0.446
Kurtosis	-1.200	0.711	-0.359	0.754	-0.042	-0.629	-0.826	-1.023
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902

The data of Sports Competitive State Anxiety variable as shown in Table 4.1 reveals that mean, standard deviation, skewness & kurtosis value of the distribution of Sports Competitive State Anxiety of the sample of 200 cases of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Zones. Nashik Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 60.32, SD 3.31, skewness & kurtosis value 0.127 & -1.200. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Nashik Zone Ball Badminton boys Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal. & Nashik Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 63.08, SD 2.34, skewness & kurtosis value 0.360 & 0.711. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Nashik Zone Ball Badminton girls Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is nearly normal.

Ahmednagar Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 66.04, SD 2.44, skewness & kurtosis value -0.237 & -0.359. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton boys Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal. & Ahmednagar Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 68.24, SD 3.21, skewness & kurtosis value 0.025 & 0.754. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton girls Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is nearly normal.

Pune District Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 58.16, SD 2.57, skewness & kurtosis value 0.237 & -0.042. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune District Zone Ball Badminton boys Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal. & Pune District Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 54.96, SD 2.42, skewness & kurtosis value -0.484 & -0.629. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune District Zone Ball Badminton girls Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal.

Pune City Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 53.76, SD 3.12, skewness & kurtosis value -0.221 & -0.826. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune City Zone Ball Badminton boys Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal. & Pune City Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Sports Competitive State Anxiety 53.88, SD 1.83, skewness & kurtosis value -0.205 & -1.023. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune City Zone Ball Badminton girls Sports Competitive State Anxiety in the present study is mostly normal.

Table no. 2

**Descriptive Statistical of the Aggression Variable for
SPPU University, Zone wise Ball Badminton Boys & Girls Players**

SPPU Zones	Nashik Zone Ball Badminton Players		Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton Players		Pune District Zone Ball Badminton Players		Pune City Zone Ball Badminton Players	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
Variable	Aggression		Aggression		Aggression		Aggression	
Gender	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
Number	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Mean	13.96	12.72	13.92	12.88	16.76	15.08	17.56	16.76
Std. Error of Mean	0.22	0.17	0.23	0.18	0.18	0.25	0.17	0.19
Median	14.00	13.00	14.00	13.00	17.00	15.00	18.00	17.00
Mode	14.00	13.00	14.00	13.00	17.00	15.00	18.00	17.00
Std. Deviation	1.13	0.89	1.15	0.92	0.92	1.28	0.86	0.96
Variance	1.29	0.79	1.32	0.86	0.85	1.66	0.75	0.94
Skewness	-0.101	-0.158	-0.010	0.254	-0.163	0.221	-0.199	0.228
Std. Error of Skewness	0.464	0.446	0.464	0.464	0.446	0.464	0.464	0.446
Kurtosis	-0.515	-0.597	-0.658	-0.132	-0.784	-0.169	-0.436	0.009
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902	0.902

The data of Aggression variable as shown in Table 4.2 reveals that mean, standard deviation, skewness & kurtosis value of the distribution of Aggression of the sample of 200 cases of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Zones. Nashik Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Aggression 13.96, SD 1.13, skewness & kurtosis value -0.101 & -0.515. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Nashik Zone Ball Badminton boys Aggression in the present study is mostly normal. & Nashik Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Aggression 12.72, SD 0.89, skewness & kurtosis value -0.158 & -0.597. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Nashik Zone Ball Badminton girls Aggression in the present study is mostly normal.

Ahmednagar Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Aggression 13.92, SD 1.15, skewness & kurtosis value -0.010 & -0.658. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton boys Aggression in the present study is mostly normal. & Ahmednagar Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Aggression 12.88, SD 0.92, skewness & kurtosis value 0.254 & -0.132. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton girls Aggression in the present study is mostly normal.

Pune District Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Aggression 16.76, SD 0.92, skewness & kurtosis value -0.163 & -0.784. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune District Zone Ball Badminton boys Aggression in the present study is mostly normal. & Pune District Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Aggression 15.08, SD 1.28, skewness & kurtosis value 0.221 & -0.169. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune District Zone Ball Badminton girls Aggression in the present study is mostly normal.

Pune City Zone 25 Ball Badminton Boys players mean value of Aggression 17.56, SD 0.86, skewness & kurtosis value -0.199 & -0.436. It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune City Zone Ball Badminton boys Aggression in the present study is mostly normal. & Pune City Zone 25 Ball Badminton Girls players mean value of Aggression 16.76, SD 0.96, skewness & kurtosis value 0.228 & 0.009 It can therefore, be said that the distribution of Pune City Zone Ball Badminton girls Aggression in the present study is nearly normal.

It was that Anxiety & Aggression are highly related to better performance in sports & games. Anxiety & Aggression contribute to enhance and down the sports & games performance.

Graph no. 1

**Sports Competitive State Anxiety Mean value for
SPPU University, Zone wise Ball Badminton Boys & Girls Players**

Graph no. 2

**Aggression Mean value for SPPU University, Zone wise
Ball Badminton Boys & Girls Players**

Graphical representation of Graph one and two Sports Competitive State Anxiety And Aggression Mean score data of Aggression variable as shown reveals that mean, standard deviation value of the distribution of Aggression of the sample of 200 cases of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Zones.

Discussion

Discussion of the results of sports competitive state anxiety & aggression inventories consist which indicate the level of anxiety and aggression of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Nashik, Ahmednagar, Pune District & Pune City Zone wise selected Ball Badminton boys and girls players as:

It was observed from the findings that the to study the effect of Anxiety & Aggression level on performance of Savitribai Phule Pune University. In the result of study from table no. 1 & 2 shown that there was Nashik Zone Ball Badminton boys & girls players level of sports competitive state anxiety was high & similar players level of aggression was low, Ahmednagar Zone Ball Badminton boys & girls players level of sports competitive state anxiety was high & similar players level of aggression was low, Pune District Zone Ball Badminton boys & girls players level of sports competitive state anxiety was low & similar players level of aggression was high and Pune City Zone Ball Badminton boys & girls players level of sports competitive state anxiety was low & similar players level of aggression was high.

Conclusion:

It was concluded that important in view of the Anxiety & Aggression in Ball Badminton Boys & Girls players of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Nashik, Ahmednagar, Pune District & Pune City Zone. Concluded that researcher evidence revealed the level of Anxiety & Aggression in Ball Badminton Boys & Girls players these Psychological variables are vital in the field of sports coaching and performance. It is known from the review of related literature that status to level of Anxiety & Aggression of sports players. It was concluded that study may help to developed efficient coaching plan for better performance consider the Anxiety & Aggression variables of the psychology.

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